

POLITICAL SCIENCES

GAS STRATEGIES: UKRAINE'S MOTIVES AND THE CONSEQUENCES FOR EUROPEAN ENERGY SECURITY

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Abstract

Ukraine has always been a transit point for transporting Russian gas to the European Union. This supply route has been functioning for more than 40 years, regardless of the international and regional situation, relations between importing countries and the main exporter of energy resources in the region. The perception of Ukraine as a major transit point has been entrenched in the minds of citizens and governments of the member countries of the European Union, no one even doubted that the situation could change. However, the beginning of 2025 showed that this situation could change dramatically. On January 1, 2025, Ukraine announced the termination of all supplies of Russian gas through its territory, which largely came as a shock to the European community.

This article is devoted to the analysis of the energy supply problem in the current regional situation, and is also an attempt to determine the true motives of Ukraine.

Keywords: gas strategies, energy crisis, economic power, European Union, transit, Ukrainian-Russian conflict.

On January 1, 2025, Ukraine refused to extend the contract with Gazprom for gas supplies to Europe via the «Urengoy-Pomary-Uzhgorod» main gas pipeline. These events triggered inevitable changes in the region's energy sector.

Gas prices are responding to this background with growth, but not as dramatic as in 2022. Then the crisis caused by the fall in Russian supplies engulfed the entire European market, and the TTF index (the largest gas hub in Europe) reached \$3,892 per 1,000 cubic meters - which is an absolute record. On February 7, TTF exceeded \$600 per 1,000 cubic meters. This happened for the first time since October 2023; at the beginning of January, the index was at \$480 per 1,000 cubic meters [1].

And although the volume of gas supplied by Russia by transit through Ukraine covered only 5-7% of the needs of the EU member states, it will still be difficult to compensate for this volume of supplies [1]. This situation will lead to the countries having to buy gas at a much higher price. It is also worth noting that, against the backdrop of the general energy crisis and the depletion of natural gas reserves, gas prices have increased by 50% over the past year, with the growth intensifying in recent months due to cold weather conditions that have led to increased demand.

Nick Thorp, BBC correspondent, spoke about the situation as follows: «As you can see, on a cold winter's day like this, it is very emotionally important. It's also strategically important, financially important in practical terms. It's the end of a five-year contract between Naftogaz of Ukraine and Gazprom of Russia. That pipeline, about three hours ago, ceased to receive gas that was passing 40 million cubic meters of gas a day through to Slovakia initially, and then on to countries like Austria, Hungary, and Italy. The European Union says it has plenty of other suppliers, notably the United States, which now supplies a great deal of gas to the

EU, but also Norway, Qatar, and other countries sending liquid gas to Europe» [2].

But strategically and symbolically, it's the end of an era because, for decades, actually since 1964, Russia has supplied Europe—initially Eastern Europe, but then Western Europe—with large amounts of cheap gas through many pipelines. Now there's only one left, supplying about 5% of Europe's needs—that's the TurkStream pipeline coming up through the Balkans. We assume the concern is that because they're now having to go to other suppliers, the cost will rise, because this has been cheap coming from Russia through Ukraine.

Obviously, the cheapest way to supply gas is through pipelines rather than to compress it, to cool it to -16° centigrade, to ship it across the sea, and then to degasify it and put it into pipelines again, which is what's now happening. Europe depends for 80% of its gas supplies on imports from other places in the world, and so the price is up. It may increase four times. Europeans pay four times more for their gas—whether that's household or industrial gas, heating gas—than the United States. And of course, that affects European competitiveness as it tries to compete with China and the United States.

Ukraine will also lose at least hundreds of millions of dollars in income that the country received for using its gas transportation infrastructure. Reuters estimated Ukraine's losses at 800 million. In addition, it will lose its status as Europe's strategic partner in providing the region with cheap raw materials from the Russian Federation.

Meanwhile, most of Gazprom's Central European clients are actively switching to alternative import sources - and paying a higher price for it. For example, Slovakia's largest oil and gas producer, «Slovensky Plynarensky Priemysel», estimated its additional costs to ensure stable supplies via various routes at 90 million

euros and warned that the risks of energy destabilization in Europe would increase in the event of a cold winter.

In turn, Russian gas continues to flow to the Hungarian market via the Turkish Stream. As the head of the Hungarian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Foreign Economic Relations Peter Szijjarto reported in January, a record 7.6 billion cubic meters of gas from Russia entered the country via this pipeline in 2024, while the capacity of the associated infrastructure on Hungarian territory is 8.5 billion cubic meters, and Budapest will provide this reserve to Bratislava. "We are increasing the annual capacity of the interconnector with Slovakia by 900 thousand cubic meters in order to be able to contribute to Slovakia's energy security," Szijjarto emphasized [3].

Let's talk about alternative routes for gas supplies from Russia. Other gas routes from Russia to Europe are also not functioning - the Yamal-Europe pipeline (via Belarus) and the Nord Stream (via the Baltic Sea). The Turkish Stream, which runs from the Krasnodar Territory of the Russian Federation along the bottom of the Black Sea to northwest Turkey, remains operational. This offshore gas pipeline later connects to the Balkan Stream, which runs from Turkey towards Hungary. Thus, the member countries of the European Union have no other way to receive Russian gas except through the Turkish pipeline, which goes through Hungary. This has led to record figures for deliveries through this gas pipeline already today.

In January, supplies via Turkish Stream increased to a record 45.2 million cubic meters per day, or 1.4 billion cubic meters per month, which is 2% higher than in December and 26% higher than in January 2024 [4]. This means that Gazprom is already using this route at a level close to the maximum possible. It is possible to further increase supplies only by using the Trans-Balkan gas pipeline and the Romanian GTS in reverse mode and partially loading the second branch of the Turkish Stream, intended for the domestic market of Turkey, for the European market.

In addition, there is a very high risk that EU countries will not be able to meet the standard for bringing the level of reserves to 90% of the nominal capacity by November 1. Experts expect it to decrease to 80-85%. As a chain reaction, this creates risks for the passage of the next heating season. Bloomberg reported in early February that European countries are struggling to meet their gas storage targets this month [5]. For example, as of February 1, underground gas storage in France was only 35.5% full, while the European Commission has set a target of 41%. In addition, the agency reported that several EU countries with the largest underground gas storage facilities, including Germany, Italy and the Netherlands, are considering relaxing storage capacity requirements after 2025. They fear that high prices make storing gas economically unprofitable.

As for alternative supply routes, experts note an increase of market interest in liquefied natural gas supplied from the United States. This will be facilitated by the low base of 2024, in which the European Union, due to high reserves in underground gas storage facilities, imported a minimal amount of American liquefied gas

since 2021. In addition, the United States, with the launch of new terminals, is entering a period of growth in LNG production, which will last for the next few years.

The main disadvantage of purchasing liquefied gas from the US is that these supplies are usually much more expensive than purchasing gas that is delivered via pipeline from Russia.

In other words, the European Union has every chance to successfully prepare for next winter, but without the restoration of gas transit through Ukraine, there is a high probability that prices will remain above \$500 per 1,000 cubic meters in the coming months.

As for Ukraine's motives in this matter, many experts are inclined to believe that Ukraine is trying to use transit as a means of influencing the EU. According to the statement of the Ukrainian President Zelensky himself, Europe is already ready to support gas supplies through alternative routes, without using the pipeline that runs through Ukrainian territory.

Although, as the information presented above has shown, Europe will be able to solve this issue, but with a lot of effort and financial losses. In any case, this is not what the EU expected from Ukraine in terms of energy supply and energy security. Especially considering the fact that in 2015 Ukraine-European Union Association Agreement was concluded between the countries, according to one of the points of which Ukraine acted as a transit point for ensuring gas supplies from Russia to Europe.

Ukraine's refusal to transit has forced European countries to choose either to use alternative, more expensive routes for gas supplies or to begin negotiations with Ukraine regarding the resumption of transit. Moreover, in their speeches, Ukrainian leaders have repeatedly pointed out the insufficient assistance of Europe regarding the Ukrainian-Russian conflict. Most likely, according to Ukrainian leaders, stopping transit should play a role in increasing the volume of financial assistance to Ukraine against the backdrop of the conflict.

To summarize, we can say the following:

Firstly, given the current situation in Europe, the main difficulties will only occur in the next heating season 2025/2026. In the current year, neither citizens nor businesses will experience a shortage of gas, because European countries have not yet used up their reserves.

Secondly, Europe actually has alternative gas supply options that countries can use to ensure production and heat in homes, however, these supply routes are not as convenient as transit through Ukrainian territory. This will make gasification more expensive and make Europe less competitive compared to China and the US.

Finally, in this situation, all parties suffer losses, including Ukraine, Russia, and the EU. The termination of transit first of all affects the energy security of the region, undermining the economic power of countries and making them more dependent on supplies from other countries.

It is also worth noting, that at the moment Ukraine has lost its status as the main transit point for energy resources. Of course, the EU will be able to find other ways to supply gas, even if they are more expensive. EU countries have economies which are strong enough

to withstand this problem. But for Ukraine, undermining its own status and stopping supplies will lead to irreversible consequences, such as worsening relations with most EU countries.

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